

STUDIES IN COMPLEX FORMATION WITH COLLOIDAL MERCURI-SULPHOSALICYLIC ACID. PART II. COMPLEX ALUMINIUM MERCURISULPHOSALICYLATE

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Colloidal mercurisulphosalicylic acid, possessing co-ordinating groups similar to sulphosalicylic acid, forms similar complexes with aluminium. Potentiometric and conductometric studies show that it forms two types of complexes: (a) 1:1 complex in acidic medium when the ratio of the metal to acid is less than 1:2, and (b) 1:2 complex when the ratio is 1:2 or more. The 1:2 complex is stable as the aluminium is not precipitated on addition of alkali. In both the complexes the phenolic hydrogen is displaced during complex formation and the co-ordination takes place between the oxygen atoms of phenolic and carboxyl groups.

In Part I of this series (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 197), the authors have reported the study of complex formation between beryllium and mercurisulphosalicylate. In this paper the physico-chemical studies on the formation of aluminium mercurisulphosalicylate in solution have been reported.

Aluminium is known to form complexes with sulphosalicylic, sulphobenzoic and sulphohydroxynaphthoic acids (Dominikiewicz, *Arch. Chem. Farm.*, 1934, 1, 92). Babko (*J. Gen. Chem.*, U.S.S.R., 1948, 18, 1617) has reported the formation of aluminium salicylate complexes. Anderson and Lasater (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1429) studied the complex aluminium sulphosalicylate spectrophotometrically, using copper sulphosalicylate complex as an indicator.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure adopted in this paper was the same as followed in the previous part (*loc. cit.*). Solutions of mercurisulphosalicylic acid and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate were prepared as described therein.

Solutions of aluminium chloride were prepared by diluting a stock solution of $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Baker's analysed), the aluminium content of which was estimated gravimetrically as $\text{Al}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN})_3$ with 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) (Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", London, 1951, p. 372).

The specific conductivity and μ_{H} measurements were made at a constant temperature of $32^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

DISCUSSION

Figure 1 represents the changes in the p_H that take place when aluminium chloride, potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate and their mixtures are titrated with alkali. The abscissa represents the number of equivalents of alkali (a) per gram ion of aluminium. Curve A is for $6.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ - $AlCl_3$ and the curves B to D are for 1:1 (Curve B), 1:2 (Curve C) and 1:4 mixtures (Curve D) of aluminium chloride and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate of the same concentrations. Curves E and F are for $6.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of mercurisulphosalicylate and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate respectively and are recorded for comparison.

FIG. 1

From Fig. 1 it may be noted that the precipitation of aluminium hydroxide starts at p_H 5.12 (Curve A), when nearly three equivalents of alkali have been added. At p_H 10.0, when four equivalents of alkali have been added, the precipitate of aluminium hydroxide dissolves to form sodium aluminate.

The neutralisation of mercurisulphosalicylate and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate has been discussed in an earlier publication (*loc. cit.*).

The 1:1 mixture of aluminium chloride and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (Curve B) has an initial p_H (2.25) which is lower than both of aluminium chloride (3.70) and potassium chloromercuri salt (2.60) alone. The curve has an inflection at $a=2$, which indicates the formation of a complex according to:

A crystalline white precipitate is obtained at p_H 4.70 and above, the quantity, however, decreases with an increase in p_H , and at p_H 9.65 no precipitate is obtained. The exact nature of the precipitate has not been investigated, but it may be some hydrolysis product of the complex formed.

The 1:2 and 1:4 mixtures of aluminium and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (Curves C & D) have again an initial p_H which is lower than both that of aluminium chloride or potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate alone. Both the curves show an inflection at $a=4$ and 6 respectively, which clearly indicates that two moles of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate react with one mole of aluminium to form a complex.

No crystalline white precipitate is obtained in both the mixtures as obtained in 1:1 mixture, showing the stability of the complex formed.

From these facts it is clear that potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate forms two types of complexes with aluminium(III): (a) 1:2 complex when the ratio of aluminium to potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate is two or more and (b) 1:1 complex when the ratio is one or more but less than two. The 1:2 complex is more stable than the 1:1 complex, as the aluminium of the former complex is not precipitated at all by alkali.

Similar results were obtained with monosodium salt of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate and Fig. 2 represents the changes in p_H when (i) aluminium chloride ($3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$) (Curve A), and (ii) 1:1 and 1:4 mixtures of aluminium chloride ($3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$) and monosodium salt ($3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$) (Curves B & C) are titrated with alkali respectively. The abscissa represents the number of equivalents of alkali added. The addition of alkali to aluminium chloride has already been discussed (vide equation 1).

FIG. 2

The 1:1 mixture of monosodium potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate and aluminium chloride (III) (Curve B) has an initial p_H (2.85) which is lower than both of aluminium chloride (3.98) and the monosodium salt (6.20) alone, which shows an increase in the hydrogen-ion concentration of the mixture. There is an inflection at one equivalent of the alkali in the p_H curve. This indicates the formation of a complex according to the equation:

A crystalline white precipitate is obtained at p_H range 4.80–6.40, above which no precipitate is obtained.

The 1:4 mixture (Curve C) has also an initial p_H which is lower than both of aluminium and monosodium salt alone, but an inflection in the curve occurs at about

$a=2$. No precipitation is observed which shows the greater stability of the complex formed. The inflection at $a=2$ shows that two moles of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate combine with aluminium to form a complex, the co-ordination taking place between the oxygen atoms of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups.

The increase in the hydrogen-ion concentration of the mixture shows clearly that the hydroxyl hydrogen is displaced during complex formation.

FIG. 3

Fig. 3 represents the changes in specific conductivity when (i) $(6.25 \times 10^{-3} M)$ aluminium chloride (Curve A), (ii) 1:1 mixture of $(6.25 \times 10^{-3} M)$ potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (Curve B), (iii) 1:1 mixture of $(6.25 \times 10^{-3} M)$ aluminium chloride and $(6.25 \times 10^{-3} M)$ monosodium potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (Curve C) and (iv) potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (Curve D) are titrated with alkali respectively. The abscissa represents the equivalents of alkali (a) added. The addition of alkali to aluminium chloride shows very little change in the conductivity in the beginning, but there are two inflections: (i) at $a=4$ showing the precipitation of aluminium hydroxide (equation 1) and (ii) at $a=3$, the formation of sodium aluminate (equation 2). The addition of alkali to potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate to (D) shows aluminium at $a=1$, according to the reaction:

The addition of alkali to 1:1 mixture of aluminium chloride with potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (B) and its monosodium salt (C) respectively shows minima in the conductivity curves at $a=2$ and $a=1$ respectively according to reactions (3) and (5). The observations provide an added evidence to the fact that the hydroxyl hydrogen is displaced during the complex formation.

Figure 4 indicates the influence of the addition of aluminium chloride in the increased quantity of the p_H of monosodium potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate.

FIG. 4

The concentration on the latter was kept constant and to it varying amounts of aluminium chloride solution were added keeping the total volume constant by the addition of calculated amount of water, and p_H values were measured in each case. The abscissa in Fig. 4 represents the volume of aluminium chloride solution and the ordinate, the p_H values. Curve A represents the p_H of the mixture solution, while 'A'' represents the p_H of aluminium chloride alone. It will be seen that the p_H of monosodium salt decreases with the addition of aluminium chloride and becomes almost constant after the addition of one equivalent (5.0 c.c.) of aluminium. Total volume in each case had been kept constant. As curve 'A' lies much below 'A'', it shows clearly that there is

an increase in the hydrogen-ion concentration of monosodium potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate on the addition of aluminium ions. This can only be explained to be due to the displacement of the phenolic hydrogen, which takes place during complex formation. The reaction may be represented by equation (5).

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